

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavan, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.
- Type all contributions double spaced.
- Indent first lines of each paragraph.
- Do not hyphenate words at the end of a line.

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Portable vacuum emasculator

*W. R. Coffman, plant breeder,
International Rice Research Institute*

The first vacuum emasculator was developed by L. E. Kirk in 1930. J. G. Van der Meulen first used one with rice in 1933 in Indonesia. The vacuum emasculator was not used extensively on rice (except in the US) until it was modified by R. M. Herrera and the author in 1974. Since that time several major rice improvement programs in Asia have obtained emasculators through IRRI and used them effectively in their crossing programs. But the IRRI model is expensive (more than US\$500) and not portable. Essentially, its use is limited to greenhouses or screenhouses with 220-V AC. That makes the vacuum emasculator impractical for many smaller programs.

The first portable vacuum

emasculator for rice was designed in the early 1950s by L. E. Crane and H. M. Beachell of Beaumont, Texas; it was later modified by J. E. Scott of the Beaumont station. Many of their ideas were used in the construction of a newer portable emasculator (Photo 1). The new model consists of a rotary vane vacuum pump that develops a continuous vacuum of 508 mm/Hg. The 12-V DC electric motor that develops 1/25 hp at 4,000 rev/min is powered by a small 12-V motorcycle battery that must be recharged periodically. Accessories include an air filter, an anther trap, tygon tubing, disposable pipette, and appropriate fittings.

The pipette is breakable. If a ready supply is not available, a large bore (#16) veterinary needle may be used instead.

The assembled unit, including the

1. A new portable vacuum emasculator.

battery and carrying box, weighs 4.4 kg. It can be carried in any convenient small box. A plastic box (Photo 2) will permit the unit to float in the paddy water, although the position of the battery must be adjusted for proper balance. One operator can emasculate 12 panicles/hour with the unit, depending on the operator's skill and other variables.

The entire unit (including the box and a small battery charger) costs about US\$150. Prices may vary, depending on the local availability of the components. The pump, motor, filter, and trap are manufactured by Gast Manufacturing Corp., Benton Harbor, Michigan, US. Units may be purchased at cost through the Plant Breeding Department, IRRI. □

2. Portable vacuum emasculator in a plastic carrying case that allows the unit to float when operated in the field.

Scientific publication among rice breeders in Asia

Thomas R. Hargrove, associate editor, International Rice Research Institute

The scientific papers or articles that 38 rice breeders had published or had accepted for publication in 1974-75 were analyzed as part of a research project on rice breeding programs in 10 Asian nations: Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Iran, Korea, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand.

The 38 scientists had authored or coauthored 183 scientific papers during the 2 years — an average of 2.4 papers/scientist per year. Fifty-three percent of the papers were published in journals within the scientist's own nation; 23% in institutional publications; 18% in journals in highly developed nations; and 6% in international publications such as the International Rice Commission Newsletter or the SABRAO Newsletter.

The distribution of publication productivity was later determined and compared with that predicted by Derek de Solla Price, who states that *half of the publications produced by a population of n scientists are authored by the most productive of about \sqrt{n} of the population*. The inverse-square root law has held true since the early scientific journals of the 17th century, but most of the research has been conducted on

chemists and physicists in the western nations.

Half of the publications were authored by only 6 of the breeders — roughly the square root of the sample of 38 breeders. And 50% of the breeders authored 11% of the total publications (see figure).

That suggests that the scientific norms of rice breeders are similar to those of other scientists, and that Asian scientists'

norms are similar to those of peer scientists in America and Europe.

When social characteristics of the scientists were compared, it was found that all the high publishers and 30% of the low publishers held the Ph.D. On the average, the high publishers were about 3 years older than the low publishers and had about 3 more years of professional experience working with rice (see table).

A study of Asian rice breeders and the scientific publications that they authored or coauthored over a 2-year period (1974-75) showed that 50% of the scientists had written or helped write 11% of the total scientific articles published by the sample; 16% had published 50% of the articles. One hundred and eighty-three scientific articles and contributions to scientific books published by 38 rice breeders at 27 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations.